

SIMULATION OF SIMULTANEOUS REPAIR AND DEGRADATION PROCESSES IN SELF-HEALING MATERIALS

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ABSTRACT

In recent years, research on self-healing materials has progressed greatly, and various systems have been proposed with different self-healing strategies. These types of materials draw inspiration from the unique properties of biological structural materials that are able to regenerate and repair themselves when damage occurs. Of course, both in biological materials and in artificial bioinspired materials, a great number of parameters contribute in determining overall macroscopic mechanical behaviour, including constituents, volume ratios, micro- and macro-structure (including hierarchical arrangements), healing rate, healing location(s) and related mechanisms. Significant advances have been made in the simulation of the mechanical behaviour of these systems in various scenarios. In the past, we have modelled both the quasistatic and the fatigue behaviour of self-healing materials using a Hierarchical Fibre Bundle Model, deriving extensions to fracture mechanics laws such as Griffith's or Paris' equations, essentially based on a single parameter, i.e. healing rate. Here, we present a continuation of these studies by adding growth and degradation evolution laws for the mechanical properties of different phases in a multi-component composite material, and present as case study that of biodegradable bioscaffolds in biological tissues undergoing self-healing, such as those used in bone or tendon prosthetics. We assume that cells are implanted onto the scaffolds, enabling their replication and growth. Thus, a previously developed elastomechanical model for cell growth, including influence of mechanical stimulation, is used to determine macroscopic material properties as a function of time and external loading. Simulation results are used to determine optimized system parameters to obtain stable mechanical properties over time during the healing period, and subsequently imposed in positive and negative modified West growth equations, which are used to model tissue growth and degradation. The proposed model can thus help guide in the choice of material combinations, structural arrangements and mechanical treatments in experimental configurations.

1 INTRODUCTION

One of the most fascinating bio-inspired properties of materials, and thus far one of the least investigated, is that of self-healing (SH) i.e. the property of a material to autonomically heal cracks, in other words to “repair itself”. This characteristic is drawn from nature where tissues like skin or bone are able to undergo long-term reparation after an instantaneous “trigger” or damaging event. Although the idea to try and replicate this behaviour in artificial materials in itself is not new, its first successful realization dates to 2001, with the work of White et al. [1], who embedded microcapsules containing a healing agent in a polymer composite, the cracking of which caused the healing agent to disperse, interact with catalysts and polymerize in the composite. This concept was subsequently further developed to study fatigue life extension due to SH in the same system, obtaining up to 90% recovery of fracture toughness [2]. With this method, healing agent depletion leads to a reduction of SH in time, so that these types of materials have a limited “working life”. Chen and co-workers developed an organic polymeric material capable of healing by heating at above 120° and then recooling, with the advantage of not requiring a catalyst [3]. All of these approaches are well suited to stopping mainly macroscopic cracks, i.e. catastrophic failure, but are scarcely effective in the case of distributed micro-cracking, as is common in fatigue experiments. “Vascular-based” SH systems were accordingly developed to mimic blood circulation in the skin healing mechanism, thus avoiding healing agent depletion and enabling repeated healing. For example, a three-dimensional microvascular network was employed to deliver the healing agent to cracks in a polymer coating [4, 5]. This technique allows repeated healing of the same crack, and has also been exploited to arrest and retard fatigue cracks [6]. Another approach to SH has been through so-called molecular-based systems. For example, Cordier et al. synthesized thermoreversible rubber that when broken or cut, can be simply repaired by bringing together fractured surfaces to self-heal at room temperature [7]. Molecular-based systems have also been developed: Burnworth et al. demonstrated the synthesis of metallo-supramolecular polymers that heal when exposed to light [8], and Chen et al. designed multiphase supramolecular thermoplastic elastomers that combine high modulus and toughness with spontaneous healing capability [9]. A comprehensive review of some of the most promising approaches to SH is given in [10].

Despite the great potential of the topic, relatively little has been done on the numerical modelization of SH. Most of the studies have concentrated on specific aspects of experiments, e.g. the modelization of the fracturing of the micro-capsules containing the healing agent, and subsequent flow of the latter. For example, Verberg et al. used a hybrid approach with a coupled Lattice Boltzmann Model (LBM) and a Lattice Spring Model (LSM) to simulate the motion of microcapsules on a substrate with an adhesive coating under the effect of an imposed flow [11]. Maiti et al. studied the behaviour of SH polymers applying coarse grained molecular dynamics on the atomistic scale in order to compute necessary parameters (e.g. local elastic modulus, reaction rates and cure kinetics) for the continuum macroscopic scale model. Balazs and co-workers developed a hybrid computational approach using LSM and the Hierarchical Bell Model (HBM) to investigate the mechanical properties and SH behaviour of nanogel particles connected by stable and labile bonds [12]. The combined LSM and modified HBM was also used to address the problem of designing strong and tough biomimetic polymer networks with the capability of reforming links in their chain [13]. A review of numerical methods applied to SH materials is given in [14]. Despite the advances obtained through these studies, much remains to be done, and numerical modelling provides the means to minimize the cumbersome efforts in experimental work, optimizing the development of materials and highlighting the most relevant features of all tested solutions. In particular, since many macroscopic properties are a result of the behaviour of the underlying nano- and micro-scale structures, a multiscale approach is essential to extract global physical and mechanical properties. In addition, due to the inherently hierarchical nature of natural materials, it is of great interest to evaluate the interaction of SH with hierarchical structure. The objective of this paper is thus to provide analytical and numerical tools to calculate multiscale mechanical properties of SH materials and discuss in particular the role of scaling, material structure and hierarchy. In particular, we apply these concepts to nanomaterials of great interest such as graphene or carbon nanotubes (CNTs), due to their particular relevance for the realization of bioinspired high-performance nanocomposites. Note that spontaneous healing mechanisms have been

found at atomic level in CNTs through interaction with a metal catalyst [15] and in monoatomic graphene sheets as a result of their interaction with metal impurities [16], and new healing strategies can be conceived, e.g. through the activation of carbon nanoscrolls [17].

Here, we present a continuation of these studies by adding growth and degradation evolution laws for the mechanical properties of different phases in a multi-component composite material, and present as case study that of biodegradable bioscaffolds in biological tissues undergoing self-healing, such as those used in bone or tendon prosthetics. We assume that cells are implanted onto the scaffolds, enabling their replication and growth. Thus, a previously developed elastomechanical model for cell growth, including influence of mechanical stimulation, is used to determine macroscopic material properties as a function of time and external loading. Simulation results are used to determine optimized system parameters to obtain stable mechanical properties over time during the healing period, and subsequently imposed in positive and negative modified West growth equations, which are used to model tissue growth and degradation. The proposed model can thus help guide in the choice of material combinations, structural arrangements and mechanical treatments in experimental configurations.

2 MODEL FORMULATION

Many biological materials (e.g. cellular protein filaments, spider silk, tendon) display a fibrous structure, and several hierarchical levels can often be identified [18-20]. On the other hand, synthetic materials of interest for structural applications are often also fibre-based (e.g. graphene/CNT macroscopic fibres or graphene/CNT-reinforced composites), and hierarchy could be an important feature for future applications [21]. Therefore, to study the process of SH, we adopt a hierarchical fibre bundle model (HFBM) which extends the classical FBM, first introduced by Daniels [22] and extensively studied during the past years (see the review [23] and references therein). This model consists of arrays of fibres having statistically distributed strengths, arranged in parallel and in series to form hierarchical architectures. The "virtual" sample is loaded parallel to the fibre direction, and the fibres fail if the load exceeds their threshold value, with the load carried by the broken fibre being redistributed among the intact ones. This model is useful to simulate damage progression in a wide range of materials, not necessarily fibrous in structure.

First, we extend the approach proposed in [24] to hierarchical materials. For a large number N_0 of fibres in a bundle, the number of surviving fibres N_{s0} , under an applied strain ε and in the absence of SH, can be assumed to be:

$$N_{s0} = N_0 \exp \left[- \left(\frac{\varepsilon}{\varepsilon_0} \right)^m \right] \quad (1)$$

where ε_0 and m are the scale and shape parameters of the Weibull distribution for the fibres [25]. By introducing Self-healing in the material and defining the number of actual surviving fibres N_{sh} , in this case, the healing parameter η can be introduced as:

$$\eta = 1 - \lambda = \frac{N_{sh} - N_{s0}}{N_0 - N_{s0}} \quad (2)$$

so that $0 < \eta < 1$. If $\eta = 0$, we have $N_{sh}=N_{s0}$ (no SH), whereas for $\eta = 1$, $N_{sh} = N_0$, i.e. all fractured fibres heal. As demonstrated in [26], we have

$$N_{sh} = N_0 \exp \left[(\eta - 1) \left(\frac{\varepsilon}{\varepsilon_0} \right)^m \right] \quad (3)$$

The introduction of SH into Eq. (11) generalizes the classical Weibull relation [25] which was used in Eq. (1), i.e. the tensile stress σ relates to an applied strain ε as:

$$\sigma(\varepsilon) = E\varepsilon \exp\left[\left(\eta - 1\right)\left(\frac{\varepsilon}{\varepsilon_0}\right)^m\right] = E_{\text{eq}}(\varepsilon, \eta)\varepsilon \quad (4)$$

where E is the single fibre Young's modulus. Thus, if the single fibre and bundle properties (E , N_0 , m and ε_0) are known, stress-strain curves (in displacement control) can be calculated. Examples of these are shown in Fig. 1 for $N_0 = 5 \cdot 10^{10}$, $E = 1$ TPa, $\varepsilon_0 = 3.4\%$ and $m = 2$, i.e. typical parameters for CNTs (also similar to graphene nanoribbon characteristics).

Figure1: Analytically-calculated stress-strain curves (in displacement control) for self-healing CNT-based specimens for various SH parameter values.

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